

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies of the Complex of Cu^{2+} Ion and 2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic Acid in Aqueous Medium

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Cu^{2+} ion forms a green, water-soluble complex with 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid with maximum absorption at 390 m μ in acidic medium. The complex is stable to wide temperature variation and at the pH range of 5.0 to 9.0. The molecular extinction coefficient is 0.54×10^4 . The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically and conductometrically, is CuR (R = reagent). The dissociation constant of the complex and its free energy of formation from Job's method are 1.99×10^{-3} and -3.71 kcal./mole at 30° , respectively. The probable structure of the complex is also suggested.

Tanabe and Hata¹ studied the colour reaction of 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid with Cu^{2+} ion and found a green colour to develop in presence of 1 to 2 drops of 28% NH_4OH , changing to reddish violet after 2 to 3 min. In a systematic study of the reaction between 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid and Cu^{2+} ion, we find that a green-coloured, water-soluble complex is formed instantaneously at the pH range of 5.0 to 6.0 and a reddish violet complex at the pH range of 9 to 11; the latter is not instantaneous and takes some hours. In view of the paucity of data about the nature and composition of these complexes, an investigation was undertaken to study the complexes spectrophotometrically, using the same methods as described in another communication². Formation of the green-coloured, water-soluble complex between 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid and Cu^{2+} in acidic medium is instantaneous. Its intensity remains constant even up to 24 hours and is stable to wide temperature variation. The complex shows the maximum absorbance at 390 m μ where the absorbance by the reagent and the metal is very small. The details of the reddish violet complex will be reported in a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

A pure sample of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H., A.R.) was used for preparing standard solutions. 2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid (R) was B.D.H., L.R. sample and was recrystallised before use. HCl, NaOH, and sodium acetate used were of B.D.H. Analytical quality.

Measurements of absorbance and conductance were made in the same way as described previously². Measurements of pH were made with a Beckman pH meter (Model H 2). All the experiments were made at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

1. *Ann. Rep. Fac. Pharm., Kanazawa Univ.*, 1956, 6, 7; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 2458^g.

2. Gupta and Soni, *this issue*, p. 311,

Spectral Studies.—Copper sulphate solution and the reagent solution ($M \times 10^{-2}$, 5 ml, each) were taken in a 25-ml flask. Suitable quantities of 1.0*M*-HCl and 1.0*M*- CH_3COONa were added so that the pH after dilution was 5.5. The complex showed the maximum absorbance at 390 $\text{m}\mu$. Similarly mixtures containing 2:1, 1:2, and 1:3 ratios of copper to the reagent were prepared as above and the absorbances at different wave lengths recorded. In all the cases studied, the maximum absorbance occurred at 390 $\text{m}\mu$, thus indicating formation of only one complex³. The wave length of 390 $\text{m}\mu$ was used for subsequent work.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentration of copper sulphate and the reagent were prepared at different pH values and the absorbances noted at 390 $\text{m}\mu$. The complex was found stable at the pH range of 5.0 to 6.0; hence a pH of 5.5 was selected for subsequent studies.

Effect of Temperature.—Mixtures were heated on a water bath to 85°, cooled to the room temperature, and absorbance was measured after making the volume. There was no difference in the absorption of the sample and that prepared at the room temperature.

FIG. 1. Job's method.
Curve 1: Cono. = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.
Curve 2: Cono. = $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$.

FIG. 2. Slope-ratio method.
Curve 1: Copper varying.
Curve 2: Reagent varying.

Composition of the Complex

Job's Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ of the metal and the reagent in which the ratios of the metal to the reagent varied from 1:9 to 9:1, keeping the pH in each case at 5.5 and ionic strength at 0.1. Absorbance was measured at 390 m μ . Curve 1 in Fig. 1 was obtained by applying this method. The maximum at 5:5 ratio of the copper to the reagent indicates formation of CuR . The same ratio was also obtained by starting with $0.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ of the metal and the reagent (curve 2, Fig. 1).

Slope-ratio Method.—The concentration of the variable component was varied from $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ in presence of the excess concentration of $5 \times 10^{-2}M$ of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was maintained at 5.5 and ionic strength at 0.1. Fig. 2 shows the measured absorbance at 390 m μ plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines provide copper:reagent ratio as 1:1.

Mole-ratio Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from $1.25 \times 10^{-2}M$ of metal and the reagent at pH 5.5 and ionic strength 0.1, as described above, and varying amounts of equimolar solutions of the metal were added such that the mole-ratio of the reagent to metal was from 1:0.2 to 1:7. Fig. 3 shows a break at a ratio of one mole of the reagent to one mole of the metal

FIG. 3. Mole-ratio method.

Copper sulphate (ml).

FIG. 4

Curve 1: Conc. = $1 \times 10^{-2}M$.

Curve 2: Conc. = $0.5 \times 10^{-2}M$.

Curve 3: Variation in pH of reagent by adding metal-solution.

Conductance Method.—Curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 4 represent the titration curves of $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ and $0.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ reagent with ten times concentrated solutions of copper sulphate, respectively. From these curves also, the ratio of the reagent to metal is found to be 1:1 which confirms the formula of the complex obtained by spectrophotometric measurements. The same formula of the complex has also been confirmed by a.c. polarography⁴.

4. Gupta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 384.

DISCUSSION

Structure of the Complex.—Fig. 4, curve 3 shows that the pH of the reagent (25 ml of $10^{-4}M$; pH 2.80) gradually decreases by addition of copper sulphate solution (0.1 M ; pH 3.0) and becomes constant at 2.6, when one equivalent of the copper sulphate solution (2.5 ml) is added. This evidently shows an increase in the H^+ -ion concentration in the mixture. This is only possible when hydroxyl hydrogen of the resorcyate is replaced by the cupric ion. This is in accordance with the view advanced by Owens and Yoes⁵ in the structure of Be-naphthazarin 1:1 complex and Be-phenoxyquinizarin sulphonate 1:1 complex. The chelation might take place as suggested below:

The dissociation constant of the complex, as calculated from Job's method at 30° and at ionic strength 0.1, is 1.99×10^{-3} . Hence the stability constant is 5.02×10^2 . Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line in which copper sulphate is varying. From Fig. 2 its value comes to be 0.54×10^4 at 390 $m\mu$. The standard free energy, ΔF° , of the complex is found to be -3.710 kcal./mole at 30° from Job's method.

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